

Forest Garden Systems and Food Forests: High Productivity on a Small Area

www.af4eu.eu

Forest garden systems like this 25-year-old example from the Lower Rhine region demonstrate that vertical layering and species diversity can create highly productive and sustainable land use systems in a small area.

Forest gardens, also known as food forests, are a diverse and sustainable model of agroforestry. They mimic natural ecosystems by combining trees and shrubs with other useful, mostly perennial plants or livestock. In Europe - especially in Germany, the Netherlands, and Ireland - they are becoming increasingly popular due to their high productivity and the wide range of benefits they offer on limited space.

Forest garden design and structure comprise a multi-layered system, typically with 5–7 layers, including (i) a canopy of tall fruit and nut trees; (ii) an understory of small trees and shrubs; (iii) an herbaceous layer preferably consisting of perennial vegetables; (iv) ground cover plants such as strawberries; (v) root crops; (vi) plant climbers such as vines and kiwis. Forest gardens are characterised by very high diversity, typically with more than 10 species per hectare, which increases their resilience to pests, diseases, and extreme weather conditions.

Forest gardens usually enhance farmers' productivity and offer economic benefits such as (i) high yields (2–5 times more biomass than monocultures thanks to vertical layering); (ii) year-round harvests (over 300 edible species and many varieties suitable for Central Europe, enabling staggered ripening and harvest times); (iii) low maintenance linked to minimal tillage, weeding, fertilizing and irrigation after establishment and (iv) provision of diverse income sources such as fruits, nuts, herbs, as well as other products and services (e.g., workshops, agrotourism).

Forest gardens also provide ecological advantages linked to (i) biodiversity (greater species diversity than monocrop systems); (ii) soil health and climate resilience improvement (soil quality, water retention, and carbon sequestration) and (iii) enhanced natural pest control through mixed cropping and companion planting.

The implementation of these highly productive and biodiverse agroforestry systems in Germany is linked to (i) urban forest gardens; (ii) individual forest garden model farms, eligible under the CAP direct payments and Eco-Schemes 3), but broader support is still needed.

Forest gardens are a sustainable, high-yield land management model that supports food security and climate adaptation. Their low resource requirements and growing demand make them a highly promising approach for cities, communities, community-supported agriculture, and farms with direct marketing.

Daniel Fischer*

Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF) e.V., working group "Agricultural Economics and Ecosystem Services"

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.